

Verification of the collision tracking feature in OpenMC with MCNPX-PoliMi and preliminary validation with a ^{252}Cf experiment

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ABSTRACT

OpenMC recently incorporated an open-source collision-tracking capability that enables filtered, per-event recording of neutron interactions for detector-response simulations. While the implementation and underlying methods were presented in previous work, its performance has not yet been verified or validated against established tools or experimental data. In this paper, we present a case verification and preliminary validation of the feature using an experimental setup using stilbene organic scintillator exposed to a ^{252}Cf source. OpenMC-generated collision files are compared directly with equivalent MCNPX-PoliMi output, showing strong agreement in deposited-energy distributions across the relevant recoil-energy range. After MPPost processing, the resulting neutron light-output spectra are compared to the measurement data. Within uncertainties, OpenMC reproduces both the MCNPX-PoliMi prediction and the experimental distribution, with only minor deviations at higher energies consistent with spectral and physics-model differences. These results demonstrate that the newly available open-source collision-tracking capability in OpenMC performs reliably for neutron light-output simulations, providing a community-driven and extensible alternative for safeguards-relevant detector modeling.

Keywords: Organic scintillator, Monte Carlo neutron transport, Collision tracking

1. INTRODUCTION

The anticipated expansion of global nuclear power capacity necessitates corresponding enhancements in safeguards activities. As part of its inspection and reactor-monitoring mandate, the IAEA has identified the modernization of safeguards technologies as a priority within its R&D roadmap [1], ensuring they remain aligned with emerging reactor concepts and technological developments. In particular, small modular reactors (SMRs) introduce new nonproliferation challenges due to their compact designs and deployment models. Safeguards measures frequently require inspectors to perform item identification and counting to verify a facility's declared inventory, making improvements in portable and robust detector systems an important area of development.

Scatter camera systems [2] can differentiate between various forms of special nuclear material and verify their proper placement [3, 4]. To simulate these systems with high fidelity, stochastic particle-transport solvers, commonly known as Monte Carlo methods, are widely used. Standard Monte Carlo approaches record averaged interaction tallies to reduce memory usage; however, the applications described above require tracking individual neutron interactions. Other applications that require individual event tracking are neutron choppers [5, 6], multiplicity counting [7], organic scintillator measurements [8, 9, 10], and noise measurements [11, 12, 13].

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In this work, we present the verification and preliminary validation of a recently implemented event-tracking capability in OpenMC [14]. The feature enables efficiently filtered collision data to be written to an external file [15]. This capability parallels the PTRAC card in MCNP [16] and the collision file in MCNPX-PoliMi [17], but with open source code and git-based development. To verify the new feature, we compare its output to that of MCNPX-PoliMi of a basic organic scintillator experiment measuring a ^{252}Cf source. The experimental data is then used to validate our approach. In Section 2 we introduce the codes and experiment in more detail, then discuss results in Section 3.

2. METHODS

2.1. MCNPX-PoliMi

MCNPX-PoliMi [17] was developed and released in 2003 to allow for event tracking and truer sampling of individual nuclear reactions, such as fission and (n,γ) as compared to the standard implementation, with the broader aim of simulating detector technologies for nuclear nonproliferation [18]. It is routinely used to model organic scintillator responses, e.g. recently in [8, 2].

2.2. The OpenMC Code

OpenMC is an open-source, community-developed Monte Carlo particle transport code for simulating neutron and photon interactions [14]. Built with scalability and high-performance computing in mind, it is well suited for modern large-scale simulations. Since its initial release in 2012, OpenMC has expanded significantly through contributions from an active international community. The code supports advanced geometry modeling, continuous-energy cross sections, and seamless coupling with multiphysics frameworks.

In the pursuit of open science and open source, we developed a collision tracking feature in OpenMC to eventually reach the same capabilities as MCNPX-PoliMi or MCNP 6.3, but with fully public git development and simpler open source licensing. The current status can be consulted in recent publications [15, 19, 20]. The implementation includes a suite of collision filters, such as reaction type, energy, cell, and material—that define which events are recorded, along with Python API extensions that simplify user input. It also provides output in both OpenMC's native HDF5 format and the Monte Carlo Particle Lists (MCPL) format.

2.3. MPPost

In this work we aim to simulate light output from neutron interactions in organic scintillator. A common simulation workflow for this purpose employs the MPPost software package [21], which processes the MCNPX-PoliMi collision output to generate detector pulse lists based on user-defined parameters. This post-processing step applies neutron light-output conversions as well as detector-specific timing and light-output resolutions to produce realistic simulated signals.

In organic scintillators, neutron elastic scattering transfers energy to recoil protons, whose subsequent interactions generate the scintillation light observed by the detector. The relationship between deposited energy and emitted light is non-proportional and MPPost models this behavior using a semi-empirical light-output function based on Birks' law [22] to convert deposited energy (MeV) into electron-equivalent light output (MeVee). The same formulation may be inverted to estimate deposited energy from measured light output. For this work, the Birks coefficients used for the stilbene were determined experimentally in previous work [23].

MPPost has been validated for a range of detector systems, including stilbene organic scintillators [23]. In this work, we use MPPost on both OpenMC and MCNPX-PoliMi outputs of the experimental geometry discussed next. Note that the OpenMC collision track output format is different from MCNPX-

Figure 1. View of the experimental setup (top) and the simulation model (bottom). Copper shielding as seen in the picture was not present for the experimental data used herein.

PoliMi, so an extra data processing step is necessary (re-arranging or adding missing columns).

2.4. Experimental setup

For experimental data and as a modeling verification test we use a single detector from the Organic Scintillator Array (OSCAR). The full OSCAR system consists of a 3x4 array of cylindrical trans-stilbene crystals (5.08 cm in diameter and 5.08 cm in length), manufactured by InRad Optics and coupled to 5.08 cm diameter photomultiplier tubes (Electron Tubes Enterprises) [24, 25, 26]. For this study, one such detector unit was used independently to acquire organic scintillator pulse data. The detector output was digitized using a CAEN V1730 waveform digitizer housed in a CAEN VME 8008B crate equipped with V6533N high-voltage modules. As source, we used a ^{252}Cf with a calculated activity of 1.86E7 Bq on the day of the experiment. Assuming a branching ratio of 3.05% for spontaneous fission, this yields a 5.67E5 fissions per second during the experiment that lasted 300 seconds. The source was set 80.6 cm in front of the detector, see Figure 1 for both a picture and view of the MCNPX-PoliMi model.

The detector was calibrated using the ~ 477 keV Compton edge from ^{137}Cs to align the gain at 1.6 V \cdot ns. The pulse-shape discrimination (PSD) results of the experiment are shown in Fig. 2. The discrimination line was determined by sampling 0.05 MeVee slices from 0 to 2 MeVee and taking the double-Gaussian centroid as discrimination line. The light output histogram of pulses classified as neutron-induced is

Figure 2. Pulse shape discrimination plot for the ^{252}Cf validation experiment. The tail integral was optimized to maximize figure-of-merit, the final value is indicated in the plot. The blue line is the used discrimination line to classify neutron-induced pulses from the gamma-ray-induced pulses.

the target validation data.

Note that for the simulations, both codes used ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data [27]. MCNPX-PoliMi uses internally stored nuclear data to generate neutrons from spontaneous fission (IPOL card), while in OpenMC we used a Watt spectrum with parameters from literature [28].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Figure 3 (left), we present the primary verification case comparing OpenMC with MCNPX-PoliMi. For an equal number of emitted source particles, we tracked the energy deposited by individual neutron interactions in the stilbene volume, mostly by proton recoils from elastic scattering on hydrogen. Over the 0.1–4 MeV recoil-energy range, the two codes show strong overall agreement, with OpenMC exhibiting a slight overcounting bias at the upper end of the spectrum. This result provides direct confirmation that the collision-tracking implementation in OpenMC is functioning as intended.

Figure 3 (right) shows the MPPost-processed collision files from MCNPX-PoliMi and OpenMC compared with experimental data. Within the reported uncertainties, both simulation results agree well with each other and with the measurement. The previously observed high-energy bias largely disappears, consistent with the reduced statistics above ~ 1.5 MeVee. These results indicate that the OpenMC collision-tracking feature is validated for neutron light-output simulations.

The differences in deposited energy may arise from discrepancies in the sampled ^{252}Cf fission spectra between the two codes, differences in the treatment of higher-energy nuclear reactions (e.g., (n,α) in surrounding materials), or simply statistical fluctuations at the higher-energy tail.

Overall, this verification and initial validation give confidence in the correctness of the OpenMC implementation. Future work will include a more detailed uncertainty analysis to further strengthen the verification and validation conclusions.

Figure 3. Tracked deposited energy by neutron interactions inside the stilbene volume (left) using the new OpenMC collision tracking feature versus the validated MCNPX-PoliMi collision file. These interactions were then processed by MPPost into light output and compared to the experimental data (right).

4. CONCLUSIONS

We verified and validated the collision-tracking capability in OpenMC that enables the recording of user-filtered neutron interactions for detector-response simulations. Verification against MCNPX-PoliMi showed close agreement in deposited-energy distributions, and further validation after MPPost-processing of the simulations demonstrated consistency with experimental neutron light-output data. Minor discrepancies at higher energies were attributed to spectral and physics-model differences or limited statistics. Overall, the results confirm that OpenMC's collision-tracking feature performs reliably for neutron detector simulations, providing a foundation for future safeguards and imaging applications. Future work will focus on a more detailed uncertainty analysis and extending this capability to additional detector types and reaction channels.

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